

Are Quantum States Ontic or Epistemic?

– A Definitive Answer –

(English version)

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Abstract

Even after a hundred years of quantum theory, the true meaning of the quantum state has not yet been clearly understood. Does a pure quantum state, described by a wave function φ , represent a real physical quantity, comparable to position or momentum in classical mechanics, or does it, even as a pure state, only have statistical significance, similar to a probability distribution?

In this paper, we show that there is no contradiction between these two interpretations. Two concepts must be distinguished here: on the one hand, physical *objects*, which have a finite lifetime, and on the other hand, *subsystems*, which are tensor factors of the Hilbert space of the universe. The complete description of an object at a certain time t is given by a linear subspace A of its Hilbert space, which, in the case of $\dim A = 1$, can be specified by a wave function φ as $A = [\varphi]$. In contrast, for every subsystem Q , every time t , and every condition \mathcal{B} , the conditional quantum state $W = W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$ can be defined as a statistical operator on the Hilbert space of Q , and this state can be used to calculate certain (conditional) probabilities. In the case of $\text{rank } W = 1$, the operator W can also be specified by a wave function φ , namely as $W = |\varphi\rangle\langle\varphi|$.

It is the subsystems of the Hilbert space that play the role of “quantum systems” in the Copenhagen formalism, and the quantum states defined for them behave exactly as described by this formalism.

If a wave function φ represents the description of a quantum object, then we are dealing with a real physical property, that is, φ plays an “ontic” role. However, if φ represents a quantum state, then its role is merely “statistical”. In this case, if condition \mathcal{B} corresponds to the knowledge of a subject, φ plays an “epistemic” role.

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An article by Pusey, Barrett, and Rudolph [2] discusses the question of whether the pure quantum state of a system corresponds to a real physical property or whether it should be understood as mere information about the system.

The authors argue that assuming even a pure state φ to correspond only to a probability distribution $\mu_\varphi(\lambda)$ for some real physical state λ contradicts the predictions of quantum theory. This is known as the “PBR theorem”.

It thus appears that the pure quantum state of a system should be understood as “ontic”, i.e., as a real physical property. This state would therefore not only have a “statistical” meaning, nor could it be understood as “epistemic”, i.e., as a mere expression of subjective knowledge about the system. However, this leaves the question unanswered as to how the sudden change of this state during measurement can be explained.

The discussion in the above-mentioned article suffers in particular from the fact that it is based on an unclear concept of the “quantum system”. It is necessary to distinguish between two different concepts here: on the one hand, quantum systems as substructures or subsystems of the Hilbert space of the universe, and on the other hand, physical objects such as electrons, protons, or billiard balls. A distinction must also be made between the quantum state (as the quantity that undergoes a sudden change during measurement) and the wave function that completely describes a quantum object at a given point in time.

In the following, we start from the canonical modeling of quantum reality as defined in [3]. According to this, we have:

- \mathcal{H} := the Hilbert space of the universe,
- \mathcal{U} := { A | A is a closed linear subspace of \mathcal{H} }
= the set of all factual properties of the universe,
- T := the time axis,
- \mathcal{E} := $\mathcal{U} \times T$
= the set of possible events.

If $(A,t) \in \mathcal{E}$ is an event, then t denotes its point in time and A denotes its *form* or *type*. The model assumption now is: Every possible event (A,t) is objectively assigned exactly one truth value in the real universe, independently of any measurements or observations.

A subsystem Q of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} corresponds to a decomposition

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_Q \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^c}$$

into two Hilbert spaces. Strictly speaking, a subsystem is an equivalence class of such decompositions (cf. [3], p. 55). For such a subsystem Q , for every point in time t , and for every sequence of events

$$\mathcal{B} = ((B_1, t_1), \dots, (B_n, t_n))$$

as a condition, one can define – in full analogy to the classical case – a *conditional probabilistic state* $W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$.

To this end, let:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_j &:= U_{-t_j} B_j && \text{(transformation to time 0)} \\
 L &:= \pi_{A_n} \dots \pi_{A_1} && \text{(combination into a single term)} \\
 W &:= LL^* / \text{tr } LL^* && \text{(state of the universe at time 0)} \\
 W_t &:= U_t W U_{-t} && \text{(state of the universe at time t)} \\
 W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}} &:= \text{tr}_Q[W_t] && \text{(state of subsystem Q at time t)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, based on the Hamiltonian H of the universe,

$$U_t := e^{-itH/\hbar}$$

is defined in the usual way as the unitary operator of time evolution. Furthermore, let

$$\begin{aligned}
 \pi_A &:= \text{the projection operator onto the subspace } A \text{ of the Hilbert space } \mathcal{H}, \\
 L^* &:= \text{the adjoint operator of } L, \\
 \text{tr} &:= \text{the trace of an operator,} \\
 \text{tr}_Q &:= \text{the partial trace on the Hilbert space } \mathcal{H}_Q.
 \end{aligned}$$

In the case of classical mechanics, conditional probabilistic states can be defined in an analogous way by letting

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{U} &:= \mathcal{B}(Z) \\
 &:= \text{the Borel algebra on } Z, \text{ the phase space of the universe,}
 \end{aligned}$$

by replacing projection operators with indicator functions, describing the time evolution by the classical law of motion, and using Lebesgue integration instead of (partial) traces. Here, a subsystem Q corresponds to a decomposition of the phase space Z into a Cartesian product:

$$Z = Z_Q \times Z_{Q^-}$$

Now, the quantum state is nothing other than this (conditional) probabilistic state in the case of quantum theory. It can be used to calculate the probabilities for possible outcomes of a quantum experiment according to the well-known formula. For this purpose, the conditions given by \mathcal{B} must correspond to the description of the experiment.

If the result of a measurement is included in the condition as an additional event, one obtains precisely the quantum state predicted by the Copenhagen formalism. Overall, the probabilistic state defined above behaves exactly as required by the quantum formalism, and for this reason it should be identified with the quantum state. For the same reason, “quantum systems” should be understood as subsystems of the Hilbert space, not as physical objects.

Thus, the quantum state is not “ontic”, simply because it refers to subsystems of the Hilbert space, which themselves cannot be regarded as “ontic”. Another reason why it cannot be interpreted as a real physical quantity is that there is a different conditional quantum state for each condition. The absolute quantum state, on the other hand, is always

trivial: it corresponds (apart from its normalization to one) to the identity operator on Hilbert space.

If the condition \mathcal{B} of a quantum state corresponds to the knowledge of a subject, then the state describes what this subject knows about the quantum system. In this case, it can be called “epistemic”. In general, however, a quantum state is merely a computational quantity that allows the calculation of (conditional) probabilities; in this sense, it is “probabilistic” or “statistical”.

Note: The calculation of outcome probabilities using a quantum state requires that the experiment be macroscopically evaluable, which means that – apart from the initial condition – both the conditions and the possible results of the experiment are documented by macroscopic events at the time of evaluation (cf. [3]).

The quantum state $W = W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$ is always a statistical operator on the Hilbert space of the quantum system Q , i.e., it is a normalized, non-negative definite operator. If W has rank one, it is a *pure* state, and it can be represented as

$$\begin{aligned} W &= \varphi\varphi^* && \text{(where } \varphi^* \text{ denotes the adjoint vector of } \varphi\text{)} \\ &= |\varphi\rangle\langle\varphi| && \text{(in Dirac notation)} \end{aligned}$$

with some wave function $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}_Q$. Except for a phase factor, φ is uniquely determined by the operator W . The wave function cannot be regarded as “ontic” here, because it only represents a quantum state that is not ontic either.

Note: In practice, a pure quantum state will always occur only as an approximation.

Let us now turn to quantum objects. These include both elementary objects such as electrons or quarks and composite objects such as protons, DNA molecules, or billiard balls. Any such physical object has to be regarded as a (possibly continuous) chain or sequence of events, i.e., as a *process*. This statement holds true in general, i.e., in every physical theory, including classical mechanics.

Unlike a subsystem Q , which has eternal existence as an abstract substructure of the Hilbert space of the universe, physical objects are limited in time. Formally, a possible object is a pair (J,A) where J is a subset of the time axis T and A is a mapping from J to the set of all factual properties of the universe:

$$A : J \rightarrow \mathcal{U}$$

The set J of points in time describes the lifetime of the object, and $A(t)$ specifies the form of the object at each time $t \in J$. This form includes all physical properties of the object, for example, (mean) position, (mean) momentum, diameter, shape, etc.

Such a possible object (J,A) may or may not actually exist. It actually exists if and only if the event $(A(t),t)$ actually occurs for all $t \in J$.

Since the event $(A(t),t)$ is completely described by its time $t \in T$ and its form $A(t) \in \mathcal{U}$ (as is every event), $A(t)$ represents a complete description of the object at time t . If one

were to understand $A(t)$ as the “state” of the object, this “state” would be ontic. However, physical objects (unlike elementary particles in classical mechanics) generally do not have self-identity. This means that the transition from one event $(A(t),t)$ to another event $(A(t'),t')$ does not occur with necessity, but only with a certain probability. For macroscopic objects, this probability can be so close to one that we have the impression of a self-identical object. In general, however, due to the lack of self-identity of objects, it makes little sense to refer to the form of an object as a “state”. Objects without self-identity are not carriers of properties that are transported over time.

Note: A classical example of an object without self-identity is a wave on the surface of water.

In the case of a moving billiard ball, the form $A(t')$ results from the form $A(t)$ by a translation in space. Since the transition probability from $(A(t),t)$ to $(A(t'),t')$ is very high, such a billiard ball appears to be a stable object. However, in the case of small particles such as electrons, the transition probability is much lower. Electrons therefore appear as volatile objects that are randomly created and destroyed.

In classical mechanics, the situation is different: while in the case of macroscopic objects the transition from one event to the next generally occurs only with a certain probability (because the composition of such an object can change over time due to interactions with its environment), this transition probability is exactly one in the case of an elementary particle. In classical mechanics, elementary particles can therefore be regarded as self-identical.

Note: The concept of a “possible object” has been introduced here in a very general sense. However, many of these possible objects bear no resemblance to what we normally imagine to be an object. In a supplementary appendix to this text, we discuss properties of possible objects that distinguish “proper” objects (such as protons or billiard balls) from “improper” ones. These include properties such as stability, structure invariance, continuity, or compactness. Examples of improper objects (i.e., entities that are not physical objects in the usual sense) are provided there as well.

Note: As we have seen, the expression $W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$ should be understood as the “quantum state” because it behaves like the quantum state does in the Copenhagen formalism. This does not apply to the form of an object: for it, there is no such thing as a “state reduction” when reading a measurement result.

We now want to consider the relationships between quantum systems (as subsystems of the Hilbert space) on the one hand and physical objects on the other. If Q is a subsystem, certain physical objects (J,A) can be *represented* by it. This is the case if $A(t)$ for all $t \in J$ has the special form

$$(*) \quad A(t) = A'(t) \otimes \mathcal{H}_Q$$

where $A'(t)$ is a subspace of \mathcal{H}_Q . In this case, $A'(t)$ completely specifies the form of the object at time t .

For example, if we want to consider an electron, we represent the Hilbert space of the universe as

$$\mathcal{H} = \otimes_e \mathcal{H}_e \otimes \mathcal{H}_{\text{rest}}$$

Here, parameter e runs through the set of all electron quanta, \mathcal{H}_e is the Hilbert space of the respective electron quantum, and $\mathcal{H}_{\text{rest}}$ denotes the Hilbert space of the rest of the universe. The latter includes all other quanta. We now select a specific electron quantum and designate it as Q . Then, an electron is an object (J,A) for which A has the structure given by (*). In this case, the subspace $A'(t)$ completely specifies the form of the electron at time t .

In certain cases, an object can be described by a wave function. This applies when $A'(t)$ has dimension one for every t . In this case, there is a mapping

$$\varphi : J \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_Q$$

such that

$$A'(t) = [\varphi(t)]$$

for all $t \in J$. Here, $[\varphi(t)]$ denotes the one-dimensional subspace generated by $\varphi(t)$. In this case, the object is completely described at time t by the wave function $\varphi(t)$, and thus this wave function plays an “ontic” role.

We will now discuss the relationship between the quantum state $W_t = W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$ defined by condition \mathcal{B} for the subsystem Q at time t and the object “prepared” by this condition. Let us assume that for every t in a time interval J we have

$$\text{rank } W_t = 1$$

so that we can represent the quantum state as

$$(**) \quad W_t = \varphi_t \varphi_t^*$$

with a wave function $\varphi_t \in \mathcal{H}_Q$. Now, let the subspace $A(t)$ be defined as

$$A(t) := [\varphi_t] \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^c}$$

for all t . In this case, the event $(A(t),t)$ will be encountered (under condition \mathcal{B}) for every $t \in J$ with probability one. The object (J,A) defined in this way is “prepared” by \mathcal{B} .

Note: In practice, equation (**) will only be valid as an approximation. Therefore, the probability of encountering the event $(A(t),t)$ is only *approximately* equal to one.

Under certain conditions, the quantum state W_t (and thus the wave function φ_t representing it) evolves according to a Schrödinger equation, which is described by a unitary operator $U'_{\Delta t}$ on \mathcal{H}_Q . We then have (for all Δt with $t+\Delta t \in J$):

$$W_{t+\Delta t} = U'_{\Delta t} W_t U'^{-\Delta t}$$

$$\varphi_{t+\Delta t} = U'_{\Delta t} \varphi_t$$

which, in practice, will also be valid only approximately.

In this case, the form of the object

$$A(t) = [\varphi_t] \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$$

transitions (approximately) into

$$A(t+\Delta t) = [U'_{\Delta t} \varphi_t] \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$$

for all Δt with $t+\Delta t \in J$, and it can be said that the prepared object moves (approximately) according to a Schrödinger equation. Here, condition \mathcal{B} prepares a *process* that satisfies the Schrödinger equation; however, it does not prepare a self-identical particle with a *state* that moves according to this equation.

Conversely, the existence of an event $E = (A(t), t)$ with the specific form

$$A(t) = [\varphi_t] \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$$

has an impact on the relevant conditional quantum state. If we include the event E as an additional condition in \mathcal{B} by setting

$$\mathcal{B}' := \mathcal{B} \cup (E) \quad (\text{as a concatenation of two sequences})$$

we obtain the conditional state

$$W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}'} = \varphi_t \varphi_t^*$$

Remark 1

In the above representation of an electron (as a physical object) using an electron quantum Q , we are dealing with an “individual” electron since we are using a specific electron quantum to represent it. However, such electrons cannot be prepared in practice, because all conditions we can have empirical knowledge of are symmetric with respect to “particle exchange”.

On the other hand, “non-individual” electrons *can* be prepared. To this end, consider the set PER of all permutations on the set of electron quanta. Each permutation $\sigma \in \text{PER}$ corresponds to a unitary operator U_σ on the Hilbert space of all electrons, i.e., on

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{electrons}} := \otimes_e \mathcal{H}_e$$

Here, parameter e runs through the set of all electron quanta. For each U_σ , we can define the corresponding unitary operator V_σ on the Hilbert space of the universe by

$$V_\sigma := U_\sigma \otimes \text{Id}_{\text{rest}}$$

where Id_{rest} denotes the identity operator on $\mathcal{H}_{\text{rest}}$.

A “non-individual” electron is now obtained by replacing the subspace $A(t)$ in the above definition of the “individual” electron with the direct sum

$$A_{\text{sym}}(t) := \oplus_{\sigma \in \text{PER}} V_\sigma A(t)$$

Strictly speaking, only such “non-individual” electrons can be prepared. However, if we assume the existence of “individual” electrons instead, we obtain, at least in certain cases, the same predictions regarding the probabilities of interest. Therefore, assuming “individual” electrons – as is normally done in the quantum formalism – can then be justified.

Remark 2

The PBR theorem cannot be applied to a quantum system, i.e., to a subsystem of the Hilbert space of the universe. A subsystem is not a physical object, and there is no physical parameter $\lambda \in \Lambda$ that (completely) describes the system. A quantum state φ therefore does not define a probability distribution $\mu_\varphi(\lambda)$ on such a parameter space Λ .

Since quantum states (understood as those quantities that undergo a sudden change during measurement) are properties of subsystems of the Hilbert space, the PBR theorem is not applicable to them either. These states have a statistical character, and the reduction of the quantum state during measurement (more precisely: when reading a measurement result) represents an epistemic process.

The PBR theorem could at best be applied to quantum objects whose form is specified by a wave function φ . (For this, quantum systems would have to be understood as quantum *objects*, not as subsystems of the Hilbert space.) However, in this case, the physical parameter λ , which completely describes the system, is identical to the one-dimensional subspace $[\varphi]$. The distribution $\mu_\varphi(\lambda)$ given by the wave function φ on the parameter space is concentrated on the single element $\lambda = [\varphi]$. Trivially, these distributions for different $[\varphi]$ do not overlap, so the argument of the PBR theorem is irrelevant here.

In order to clarify the question of whether the (pure) quantum state is to be understood as “ontic”, “statistical”, or “epistemic”, the reasoning of the PBR theorem is of no help since it is not clearly defined there what is meant by a quantum system and then by a quantum state.

Summary

Quantum systems are specific substructures of the Hilbert space of the universe. For every such quantum system Q , every point in time t , and every condition \mathcal{B} (i.e., every finite sequence of events), there is a uniquely defined quantum state $W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$. This state behaves as described by the Copenhagen quantum formalism. Like the quantum system Q , it is not “ontic”. Rather, it is a mere computational quantity that allows certain probabilities to be predicted. Therefore, it can be regarded as “statistical”. If condition \mathcal{B} corresponds to the knowledge of a subject, it can also be called “epistemic”. After reading a measurement result, the subject will be interested in a new, extended condition and therefore in a different quantum state. Thus, the “reduction” of the quantum state is an “epistemic” process.

A quantum object, such as an electron, a molecule, or a billiard ball, is a *process*, i.e., a sequence of events. Each event has a time t as well as a form that is (completely) described by a subspace A of the Hilbert space. Therefore, every object also has, at every time t

within its lifetime, a form $A(t)$ that describes it completely. This form has to be regarded as “ontic”.

In certain cases, a quantum state W can be represented by a wave function φ as $W = \varphi\varphi^*$. In this case, the wave function plays not an ontic but a statistical (and possibly an epistemic) role. However, if the form A of an object is represented by a wave function φ , in particular as

$$A = [\varphi] \otimes \mathcal{H}_Q \quad (\text{with a subsystem } Q \text{ of the Hilbert space of the universe})$$

then the wave function plays an ontic role.

Therefore, the question of whether “the” wave function plays an ontic or a statistical role is a false alternative that can be resolved. The PBR theorem does not help in this situation, as it is not clear what is meant here by a quantum system and then by a quantum state.

If quantum physics assumes that a physical object can be completely described by a wave function and, on the other hand, understands the reduction of a quantum state as “epistemic”, there is no contradiction: Quantum systems have quantum states, but they are mere formal substructures of the Hilbert space of the universe, not physical objects. The reduction of a quantum state is an epistemic process. Quantum objects, in contrast, have no self-identity. They do not have a quantum state, but rather a *form* at every point in time that completely describes them. In certain cases, this form can be specified by a single wave function.

References

- [1] R. Lierenfeldt: *Sind Quantenzustände ontisch oder epistemisch? – Eine definitive Antwort*. In: R. Lierenfeldt: *Are Quantum States Ontic or Epistemic? – A Definitive Answer*. (2024). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10694813>
- [2] M. F. Pusey, J. Barrett, T. Rudolph: *On the reality of the quantum state*. (2012). Nature Phys. 8, 475–478. arXiv:1111.3328v3 [quant-ph]
- [3] R. Lierenfeldt: *Realistic Quantum Theory: Solving the Interpretation Problem. English version*. (2026). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18644694>

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Appendix: Proper and Improper Objects

The concept of “possible objects” has been introduced here in a very general sense. However, many of these possible objects bear no resemblance to what we normally imagine to be a physical object. In this appendix, we will discuss properties of possible objects that characterize “proper” objects (such as protons or billiard balls) as opposed to “improper” ones.

In general, a possible object is a pair (J, A) with a lifetime $J \subset T$ and a mapping $A : J \rightarrow \mathcal{U}$ that specifies the form of the object at each point in time $t \in J$ as $A(t)$. If the object is described by a subsystem Q of the Hilbert space of the universe, then for each $t \in J$ there is a subspace $A'(t)$ of \mathcal{H}_Q that satisfies

$$A(t) = A'(t) \otimes \mathcal{H}_Q^-$$

When we speak of an object here, we always mean a *possible* object, regardless of whether this object actually exists or not. Moreover, it is irrelevant here whether the object can be observed or not. In particular, the observability of microscopic objects is quite limited.

We expect objects in the true sense to have a certain degree of *stability*. This means that they should exist for at least a certain period of time. This is the case if the following holds: If t_0 is a point of time in J , for example the starting point $t_0 = \min(J)$, and the “initial event” $(A(t_0), t_0)$ has actually occurred, then for all $t \in J$, the event $(A(t), t)$ should also occur with a high (transition) probability. In general, this is true only under a certain condition \mathcal{B} . Stability of the object can be understood here to mean that a random decay of the object is unlikely. An object that is stable in this sense can be seen as “approximately self-identical”. If its initial event has occurred, then (under condition \mathcal{B}) it will be encountered with high probability throughout its entire lifetime J .

This case occurs, for example, when the following applies:

- (i) Under condition \mathcal{B} (and regardless of whether the initial event occurs), the subsystem Q , i.e., its quantum state, evolves approximately according to a Schrödinger equation with some Hamiltonian H' on \mathcal{H}_Q .
- (ii) With the definition $U'_\tau := e^{-i\tau H'/\hbar}$ (for all $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$), we have for every $t \in J$:

$$A'(t) = U'_{t-t_0} A'(t_0)$$

i.e., the possible object described by $A'(t)$ moves according to this very Schrödinger equation.

In this case, we are dealing with an object that will be encountered with high probability (under condition \mathcal{B} , due to (i)) and moves according to the Schrödinger equation.

The “stability” of this object does not preclude changes in its form (which includes its position and momentum, for example). Stability only means that there are high transition probabilities from one object-event to the next. If, on the other hand, the form does *not*

change, the object is called *form-invariant*. This applies, for example, if in addition to (i) and (ii) we have $A'(t) = [\varphi]$ for all $t \in J$ with one specific eigenfunction φ of the Hamiltonian H' . In this case, the form of the object remains unchanged over time, i.e., the object is form-invariant, comparable to a standing wave.

An example of a stable object is an electron orbiting the nucleus of an atom as a bound particle. In this case, condition \mathcal{B} specifies that the nucleus is present and that there are no disturbing interactions. If the form of the electron is given by an eigenfunction of the associated Hamiltonian, then the electron is form-invariant. Thus, the role of the eigenfunctions of the Hamiltonian is to describe form-invariant objects.

If the subsystem Q under consideration represents a composite object, e.g., a proton consisting of three quarks, then Q can be decomposed into two further subsystems X and S . Here, X represents the position and momentum of the entire system in space, while S describes all other degrees of freedom and thus the internal structure of the system. We then have:

$$\mathcal{H}_Q = \mathcal{H}_X \otimes \mathcal{H}_S$$

We now further assume that $A'(t)$ can be represented for all $t \in J$ as

$$(+) \quad A'(t) = A_X(t) \otimes A_S(t)$$

with subspaces $A_X(t) < \mathcal{H}_X$ and $A_S(t) < \mathcal{H}_S$. If we then have $A_S(t) = C$ for all $t \in J$ with a fixed subspace $C < \mathcal{H}_S$, the object under consideration is *structure-invariant*, i.e., it retains its structure while it can move in space. In this case, the subspace C describes the structure of the object.

In particular, we can consider the case where $A'(t)$ has the form given by (+) and the subsystem S (under the given condition \mathcal{B}) evolves – independently of the subsystem X – according to a Schrödinger equation with a Hamiltonian H_S on \mathcal{H}_S . Now, if φ is an eigenfunction of H_S and $A_S(t) = [\varphi]$ holds for all $t \in J$, the object is structure-invariant, i.e., its structure remains unchanged over time.

An example of this is a proton, which can move freely in space as a whole system, but whose internal structure (as a system of three quarks) evolves according to a Schrödinger equation with a Hamiltonian H_S on \mathcal{H}_S . In this case, condition \mathcal{B} only specifies that the surrounding space is more or less empty and that there are no disturbing interactions. The structure of the proton at time t is given by the subspace $A_S(t) < \mathcal{H}_S$.

One can only speak of a “proton” in the true sense if this structure describes, at every point in time, a configuration in which the quarks involved are bound to one another. Here, the same applies as for macroscopic objects: by definition, a billiard ball only exists if the elementary particles involved are bound to one another in a certain way.

If there is an eigenfunction φ of the Hamiltonian H_S such that $A_S(t) = [\varphi]$ for all $t \in J$, then the structure of the proton remains unchanged over time. For such a structure-invariant proton, one can ask, for example, what its average diameter is. The diameter is an “observable” D here, i.e., a self-adjoint operator on \mathcal{H}_S . It is a quantity that indicates the approximate extent of the proton’s interaction; for example, D can be defined as the maximum distance between the quarks involved. For the quantity D , the wave function φ defines a distribution $\mathfrak{B}_\varphi(D)$ on \mathbb{R} and thus a mean value, i.e., the expected value $E_\varphi(D)$. In principle, this value can be determined both theoretically and experimentally.

Another example is a DNA molecule that can move freely within a cell on the one hand and has a stable structure on the other. Since there will normally be exactly one molecule of the same type in the cell and the number of these molecules is a constant of motion, this DNA molecule can be regarded as a self-identical object. Such a molecule can be imagined as an object that moves randomly within the given area of the cell, while its structure (and thus its genetic information) remains intact over a long period of time.

This example illustrates how biological phenomena can be understood within the framework of the realistic quantum theory that underlies the present discussion. In a similar way, objects that occur in other areas of natural science can also be understood on the basis of this theory.

In addition to the aspect of stability, there are other properties that a possible object should have in order to be considered an object in the true sense. For example, we also expect such an object to be continuous, which means that A is a continuous mapping from J to \mathcal{U} . Here, the metric distance on \mathcal{U} is defined as

$$d(A,B) := [\operatorname{tr} (\pi_A - \pi_B)^2]^{1/2}$$

We also expect proper objects to be compact. An object is compact if its lifetime J is an interval $[t_a, t_e]$ and its form $A'(t)$ is compact at every point in time $t \in J$. This means the following: For an elementary particle, each wave function φ defines a distribution $\mathfrak{B}_\varphi(X)$ on physical space (on \mathbb{R}^3). This distribution can be interpreted as a mass distribution. For a subspace $A' < \mathcal{H}_Q$, we also obtain such a mass distribution. If this distribution is concentrated on a finite and connected spatial area, then A' is compact in the sense we understand it here. The same considerations apply to composite objects, such as a salt crystal.

By contrast, examples of non-compact “objects” are:

- a) Electrons whose form is represented by a bimodal wave function, i.e., by a wave function φ that defines a bimodal distribution $\mathfrak{B}_\varphi(X)$. If, for example, φ_1 and φ_2 are two wave functions, each of which describes a unimodal (compact) mass distribution, but which are concentrated in two areas far apart from each other, by forming the superposition

$$\varphi = (\varphi_1 + \varphi_2) / \sqrt{2}$$

we obtain a bimodal wave function.

b) A pair of two entangled electrons that are far apart from each other also represents a non-compact object.

These delocalized, non-compact objects can be regarded as “improper”. Objects of this type can be stable in the sense described above, even if they do not meet the requirement of compactness. By the way, there is nothing strange about improper objects. It is simply a matter of definition whether we choose to regard a (possible) object as “proper” or “improper”.

Note: When considering non-compact objects, one should be aware of the following: In quantum theory, there are no *point-like* local events or objects (“point masses”). However, if an object is concentrated exclusively in a specific region D of spacetime, the effect of the presence of this object is limited to the light cone originating from D . This light cone is defined as the union of the light cones of all points that belong to D . In this way, quantum theory is local in the sense of special relativity.

Note: An object is macroscopic if $A(t)$ is a macroscopic property of the universe for every $t \in J$. However, certain microscopic objects can also be regarded as objects in the true sense; proper objects do not generally have to be macroscopic.

Another example of “improper” quantum objects are those that (unlike “normal” objects) do not have a limited lifetime $J \subset T$, but are defined on the entire time axis. To discuss this, let us consider a possible event (A,t) with a subspace A of \mathcal{H} and $t \in T$. Let $J := T$ and for all $t' \in T$ let:

$$A(t') := U_{t'-t}(A)$$

where U_{τ} (for all $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$) is the unitary operator of motion for the universe as a whole.

Then, formally, the pair (J,A) is a possible object. If the event (A,t) actually occurs, this object is real, and it exists eternally since J coincides with the entire time axis. Furthermore, it is absolutely stable because (due to Schrödinger’s equation) the transition probability from one event $(A(t'),t')$ to the next $(A(t''),t'')$ is exactly equal to one. Such objects are the only ones that can be considered self-identical in the strict sense in quantum theory. In general, they do not refer to a proper subsystem of the Hilbert space of the universe, but to the universe as a whole. They can therefore be called “universe-objects”. However, they bear no resemblance to what we would normally consider an “object” (such as a proton or a DNA molecule).

Note: Based on the above definitions, every actual event can be extended to a universe-object that exists throughout the entire time axis T . We may even say that the universe consists of nothing else but such eternal universe-objects.